

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Summary

We provide 4 recommendations on the use of liquid biopsy that involve 1) the application of reference material, 2) reporting of molecular test results from cfDNA analyses, 3) external quality assessment for liquid biopsy laboratories, and 4) monitoring therapy efficacy using serial ctDNA liquid biopsies for metastatic colorectal cancer patients.

Background

Precision cancer medicine entails tailored-treatment selection based on specific tumor characteristics and has contributed to the improvement of treatment outcomes of patients with cancer, in particular in non-small cell lung cancer, breast cancer, and colorectal cancer. With the rapid expansion of clinically relevant biomarkers in various cancer types, genomic profiling is becoming a necessity to guide treatment and the clinical decision-making process in an increasing number of malignancies. Although predictive biomarker testing conventionally involves tissue-based testing, in recent years, liquid-based testing, mostly the analysis of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA), has been translated into the clinic. Initially, single biomarker tests to interrogate single genes or few hotspots in plasma-derived circulating cell-free (ccfDNA) were approved as companion diagnostic for molecular targeted drugs. However, with the ever-growing number of actionable gene alterations and pan-cancer biomarkers both tissue and ctDNA testing are moving towards comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP), typically carried out with next-generation sequencing (NGS). Unlike traditional single-gene tests, CGP provides a broad picture of the genetic alterations and enables the detection of all main classes of genomic alterations. However, the interpretation is complex and ctDNA-based liquid biopsy still lacks the necessary standardization for Europe-wide clinical trials. Therefore, in order to make liquid biopsy-based personalized cancer medicine more accessible and eventually available to all, the European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS) has defined a number of recommendations within the CAN.HEAL project.

Objective of the deliverable

These guidelines will provide further standardization of liquid biopsy assays necessary for clinical implementation.

Work performed and Results

1. ctDNA reference materials

As with any test entering the clinical practice, ctDNA-based assays require standardization and quality assurance. Therefore, for routine use, the analytical validity of a ctDNA test including the assessment of a test's accuracy and robustness, limit of quantification (LoQ), sensitivity or limit of detection (LoD), specificity or limit of blank (LoB) need to be established within the testing laboratory. However, due to the dependence on various preanalytical variables and protocols for sample preparation, ctDNA detection assays have been difficult to analytically validate. The most ideal control material would be patient plasma samples including replicates in the clinically relevant ctDNA fraction and this is feasible for small numbers of laboratories. However, this is a finite resource and the generation of contrived samples may be resource intensive. Therefore, a good quality control material would be a material that resembles authentic circulating DNA fragments

in cancer patients with respect to biochemical properties of cfDNA. Furthermore, the reference materials must be available with different levels of various known genetic alterations and/or no variant within the region of interest (wild type) to assess the analytical performance of a test. However, currently there is no consensus about the origin or make up of such reference materials. The European Liquid Biopsy Society ctDNA Workshop in 2023 brought together 44 experts from various disciplines to discuss the current status and future needs for reference materials in cancer liquid biopsy assays.

Recommendation: The experts emphasized the importance of using reference materials that closely mimic patient-derived ctDNA in terms of biochemical properties and assay performance and recommended the use of plasma-like reference materials, multiple serial dilutions, and various input amounts to assess analytical sensitivity and specificity.

2. Reporting of molecular test results from cell-free DNA analyses

The implementation of circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) in the diagnostic routine may enable non-invasive predictive biomarker testing and treatment optimization in patients who lack a suitable tumor specimen, have failed previous molecular analysis or are clinically ineligible for (re-)biopsy procedures. As the interpretation and reporting are more complex for ctDNA than conventional tissue-based NGS, there is a need for specific guidelines. These will offer support for the reporting of ctDNA test results and will facilitate optimal communication of liquid biopsy findings between diagnostic laboratories and the medical oncology team. Aiming to generate guidelines based on real-world experiences and broad perspectives, we organized a European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS) ctDNA workshop, in which forty-four experts and key stakeholders from different molecular diagnostics laboratories, oncology and pathology departments, as well as an IVDR specialist, convened to address significant challenges associated with the reporting of liquid biopsy test results.

Recommendation: Reports of predictive liquid biopsy biomarkers need to be accurate from a technical perspective, but ultimately serve to benefit the patient. Therefore, these reports need to be integrated in an optimal treatment decision workflow. To achieve this, it is foreseen that the collaboration and communication between clinical scientists, (molecular) pathologists, geneticists and oncologists will further intensify in the near future due to the specific nature of ctDNA testing, that adds several layers of clinical pathological complexity not generally present in tumor tissue testing. To address significant challenges associated with the reporting of liquid biopsy test results, we recommend the following. Practical responsibilities for (medical) oncologists requesting ctDNA testing include providing relevant clinical information to the testing lab. Appropriate information should also be given to the patients regarding the advantages and limitations of ctDNA testing, with explicit recognition of the possibility of unexpected and incidental findings. For clinical scientists (molecular), pathologists, and geneticists, key challenges of ctDNA test reporting include the management of variants detected at low VAF, potential CH-derived variants, SCNA and fusions, with adequate (but concise and synoptic) description of their relevance, resulting in unequivocal communication with the treating physician, and hence the patient. Oncologists and laboratory personnel altogether need to be aware of challenges and potential uncertainties of test results. Clinical scientists, (molecular) pathologists, and geneticists should provide oncologists with adequate support for the interpretation of ctDNA test reports, with which many oncologists may be unfamiliar. Vice versa, the clinical

oncologist must devote effort in illustrating the complexity of clinical cases to the clinical scientists, (molecular) pathologist or geneticist, resulting in a continuous bilateral communication before, during, and after diagnostic reporting. Complex or rare ctDNA test results should be discussed in MTBs, in the presence of pulmonary oncologists, medical oncologists, geneticists, clinical scientists, pathologists and other health professionals, as appropriate for each clinical case.

Published in: de Jager, V.D., et al., Reporting of molecular test results from cell-free DNA analyses: expert consensus recommendations from the 2023 European Liquid Biopsy Society ctDNA Workshop. EBioMedicine, 2025. 114: p. 105636.

3. External Quality Assessment (EQA) for Liquid Biopsy assays

After implementing a ctDNA test in medical laboratories, continuous external quality control is essential to maintain high standards in biomarker testing and reporting. External quality assessment (EQA), also known as proficiency testing (PT), ensures this through an independent audit of laboratory services. EQA is particularly crucial for biomarker testing in plasma samples when patient management relies on accurate testing and needs to evolve from single-gene/variant detection to multi-marker analysis. Although EQA schemes for ctDNA are available from several EQA providers, most schemes only cover single or a few genomic biomarkers. Due the growing number of actionable biomarkers, liquid biopsy based comprehensive genomic profiling (CGP) of tumour DNA is becoming increasingly important for therapy guidance and is therefore often considered complementary to tissue testing. Therefore, there is growing need to expand EQA schemes to support more comprehensive clinical testing scenarios. The European Liquid Biopsy Society (ELBS) ctDNA Workshop in 2023 brought together 44 experts from various disciplines to discuss the current status and future needs for external quality assessment (EQA) in cancer liquid biopsy assays.

Recommendation: A key priority is the inclusion of a broad range of clinically actionable genomic biomarker in routine EQA programs, alongside standard clinical case referrals. Furthermore, it has been recognized that the inclusion of the rare or technically challenging variants, as well as complex clinical cases, is a crucial responsibility of the EQA provider. This ensures that participating laboratories have opportunities to evaluate their capability to handle such cases, while also providing guidance where deficiencies are identified. The fundamental remit of EQA is to assess the quality of the testing service provided and to promote the education of the partners involved in delivering to ensure the patient receives the highest quality of service.

4. ctDNA to monitor therapy efficacy: metastatic colorectal cancer use-case

The response to systemic therapy against metastatic colorectal cancer (mCRC) is currently assessed by radiologic imaging. However, an increasing number of studies have shown that circulating tumor DNA (ctDNA) as liquid biopsy can be used as an alternative method to assess therapy efficacy. Nevertheless, the need for accurate quantification of the success of ctDNA based evaluation on therapy outcome is still necessary. Additionally, current studies are highly heterogenous in terms of type of treatments, analytical methods, analysis markers, sampling frequencies, and follow-up periods. It is therefore critical to discuss the necessity for standardization of quantification parameters for long-term adoption of ctDNA-based monitoring in clinical trials. We conducted a systematic review

with subsequent meta-analysis of primary studies to assess the predictive value of sequential liquid biopsies in patients with metastatic colorectal cancer treated with systemic therapy. Our analyses contained 54 studies involving 4144 evaluable patients with metastatic colorectal cancer that could be included in the meta-analysis. ctDNA increase during systemic therapy as compared to baseline was strongly associated with progression-free survival (HR: 2.44, 95%CI: 2.02-2.95) and overall survival (HR: 2.55, 95%CI: 2.01-3.24), which were reported in 31 and 22 studies, respectively.

Recommendation: Our findings confirm the prognostic value of longitudinal ctDNA analysis through liquid biopsy in metastatic colorectal cancer. Subsequent research should evaluate ctDNA's role in guiding therapeutic decisions, particularly in identifying patients likely to benefit from treatment continuation or regimen modification. While further standardization and validation through randomized controlled trials are warranted, based on the available data, we recommend integrating serial ctDNA monitoring in randomized controlled clinical trials for therapy guidance and future iterations of the RECIST criteria.

Main achievements

All guidelines will be published in peer-reviewed, scientific journals, making them accessible to everyone. The guidelines on the reporting of molecular test results from cell-free DNA analyses have recently been published in eBioMedicine (see above), whereas all other guidelines have either been submitted for publication or are currently in revision.

Impact

These guidelines are providing further standardization of ctDNA-based liquid biopsy assays necessary for implementation in clinical trials.

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